

Sunan Ampel Great Mosque, Surabaya

also known as "Ampel Mosque", "Masjid Agung Sunan Ampel"

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Entry tags: Southeast Asian Religions, Religious Place, Sufi, Shrines, Religious Group, Islamic Traditions, Tomb

Sunan Ampel (1401-1478, also known as Raden Rahmat or Soenan Ngampel) was the son of Sunan Gresik (also known as Maulana Malik Ibrahim Asmarakandi) and the Champa princess Dewi Candrawulan. Sunan Gresik and his descendants collectively constitute the Wali Songo (revered saints of Islam on the island of Java). Each saint bore the Javanese honorific Sunan. Sunan Gresik was instrumental in the proselytization of the Champa kingdom and its inhabitants to Islam. Dewi Dwarawati, Raden Rahmat's aunt (Dewi Candrawulan's sister) was the consort of the Majapahit monarch Brawijaya. In 1443, upon arrival in Java, Brawijaya granted him land in Ampel Denta, Kahuripun (that corresponds to modern Surabaya). Raden Rahmat subsequently entered into a matrimonial alliance with a Javanese princess who was the sister of the would-be Sunan Kalijaga. According to the Babad Ngampeldenta (Javanese chronicle), Raden Rahmat was invested with the Javanese appellation of Sunan by his uncle Brawijaya. The title Sunan mediated his position not only as an Islamic teacher but also someone who had the authority to impart Diksa or induct students into Islam. Furthermore the Babad Ngampeldenta notes the investiture of Raden Rahmat with the title "the Imam of Surabaya" by the Duke of Surabaya Aria Lembasura. At the same time, Aria Lembasura offered his granddaughter Nyai Ageng Manila in matrimonial alliance to Sunan Ampel. With Nyai Ageng Manila, Sunan Ampel begot Sunan Drajat and Sunan Bonang. Sunan Ampel's closeness to the royal family was a part of his Dakwah or Daawa strategy (the act of calling people to embrace Islam). Prior to settling in Surabaya, Sunan Ampel mentored Raden Patah, the son of Brawijaya and converted him to Islam. The latter subsequently refused to acknowledge the suzerainty of the Majapahit monarch. The act of Raden Patah's defiance later led to the establishment of the Sultanate of Demak by 1478. A salient feature of Sunan Ampel's dakwah was the syncretism between Javanese cultural traditions (heavily influenced by Hinduism and Buddhism) and Islam. For instance, he incorporated the Javanese custom of Sraddha (homage paid to one's deceased ancestors). Historical tradition attributes the construction of the Ampel mosque to Sunan Ampel. The monument cannot be precisely dated. The mosque architecture is a fusion of Javanese and Arab elements. The Javanese influences are apparent in the three-layered roof (Tajuk, the embodiment of Mount Meru of Javanese cosmology) and the five gapuros (entrance gates) to the mosque. The tomb of Sunan Ampel is situated right in front of the Ampel mosque. Unlike the tombs of other Wali Songo, the tomb of Sunan Ampel is noted for its simplicity and lacks a cupola as per the saint's last wish. The Juru Kunci (caretaker of the shrine) notes that several years after the demise of Sunan Ampel, a cupola was constructed above the tomb of the saint but strong winds blew it away. East of the mosque is the tomb of Mbah Shonhaji or Mbah Sholeh, an astronomer of Hadhramaut Arab ethnicity and disciple of Sunan Ampel who fixed the direction of Kiblat (Qibla, the fixed direction to Kaaba in the Grand Mosque in Makkah). According to legend, Mbah Shonhaji was believed to have lived and died nine times and as a result has 9 tombs in the Sunan Ampel masjid complex.

Date Range: 1421 CE - 2021 CE

Region: Eastern Java

Region tags: Asia, Southeast Asia, Indonesia, Java

The shaded area includes the political core of the Majapahit Empire at the turn of the 16th c, centered on the eastern half of the island of Java. The Shrine of

Sunan Ampel is situated in the city of Surabaya.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: No

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Not applicable.

↳ A group of structures:

– I don't know

↳ A group of features:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The Sunan Ampel Great Mosque, the Gapuro, and the tombs of Sunan Ampel, Nyi Gede Manila and his disciples Datok Ibrahim and Mbah Shonhaji.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The word antiquity and modernity do not apply to historical understanding of Java.

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Agus Sunyoto, *Atlas Wali Songo: Buku Pertama Yang Mengungkap Wali Songo Sebagai Fakta Sejarah* (Bandung: Pustaka IIMaN, Trans Pustaka dan LTN PBNU, 2017).

Notes: Agus Sunyoto's *Atlas of Wali Songo* highlights the syncretism of Sunan Ampel's Dakwah.

– Source 1: C. Spat, *De Islam en Zijn Beteekends voor Nederlandsch Indie* (Breda: De Koninklijke Militaire Academi, 1925)

Notes: Brief description of two influential pupils of Sunan Ampel: (a) Raden Pakoe, who later became famous as Sunan Giri; and, Raden Patah, who played a major role in the downfall of the Majapahit.

– Source 1: Anna M. Gade, "Sunan Ampel of the Javanese Wali Songo," in *Tale of God's Friends: Islamic Hagiography in Translation*, John Renard edited (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2009).

Notes: Gade notes that Raden Rahmat (Sunan Ampel) belonged to the earlier generation of Wali Songo as he was the teacher of other members of the Wali Songo particularly Sunan Giri, Sunan Bonang and Sunan Drajat. His father came from Samarkand (now in Uzbekistan) whereas his mother was a Champa Princess (a kingdom that is today located in Cambodia and Vietnam). Raden Rahmat's parentage represents the transnational character of Islam in maritime Southeast Asia. Among the tales of the Wali Songo, his style and effectiveness in preaching Islam emphasizes Sharia-mindedness. His aunt Dwarawati (also a Champa princess) was the consort of the Majapahit monarch Brawijaya. His uncle permitted him to settle in the region around Surabaya. He used extraordinary means to further dakwah such as crafting rattan fans and handing them to locals for free upon utterance of the words of the Shahada (Islamic oath) in exchange. The rattan fans crafted by Raden Rahmat had miraculous ability in

curing cough and fever. Raden Rahmat settled in the village of Ampeldenta, formerly used to train Majapahit nobles who wished to become teachers, and became famous as Sunan Ampel. In his teachings, Sunan Ampel emphasized the importance of moral character. He taught his disciples how to perform acts of worship in accordance with Islam. Sunan Ampel invited the Majapahit monarch Brawijaya to convert to Islam but the latter declined. Apart from dakwah, Sunan Ampel developed Arabic-derived script (Huruf Pegon) used for writing the Javanese language. The gist of Sunan Ampel's philosophy can be summarized as : (a) Dzatul Wujud (essential being), a quality that can be apparent only at the moment or extinction; (b) tawhid (divine unity); and, (c) marifat (spiritual knowledge). The younger generation of the Wali Songo, particularly Sunan Bonang, Sunan Kudus and Sunan Muria, were ingenious in adapting Islam to Javanese culture. On the contrary, Sunan Ampel, Sunan Giri and Sunan Drajat were uncompromising in matters related to Islamic customs or revealed laws of Islam. The styles of dakwah among the older and younger generations of Wali Songo differed significantly.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1163/22134379-90003641>

Notes: Ronit Ricci, " Conversion to Islam on Java and the Book of One Thousand Questions," *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land-en Volkenkunde* 165, no. 1 (2009): 8-31. The Babad Tanah Jawi corpus, of which many versions exist, recounts Javanese history from the days of Adam to the eighteenth-century kings of Mataram, including the transition from Hindu-Buddhist rule to the rise of Islamic states on Java. Although its earliest known versions were written long after the events depicted, it provides at the very least a glimpse of certain ways in which the spread of Islam on Java was remembered.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– I don't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– I don't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Field does not know.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

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Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: No

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Not applicable.

↳ A group of structures:

– I don't know

↳ A group of features:

– Field doesn't know

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Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The word antiquity and modernity do not apply to historical understanding of Java.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

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– I don't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

–Other [specify]: Field does not know.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Prasasti or inscription in Pegon (modified Arabic script) in Javanese language. See for e.g. Iva Istiqomah, *Prasasti Masjid Agung Sunan Ampel Surabaya : Studi Tentang Kontak Peradaban Antara Jawa, Arab Dan Barat Dalam Kronologi* (Undergraduate thesis, UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya, 2014).

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Not applicable.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– I don't know

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– I don't know

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Notes: For e.g. each of the five Gapuros of the Ampel mosque represent a tenet of Islam: (a) Gapuro Puso (fasting); (b) Gapuro Madep (prayers); (c) Gapuro Mungguh (Haj pilgrimage); (d) Gapuro Ngamal (pious deeds); (e) Gapuro Panekan (credo).

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– I don't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– I don't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Not applicable.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Teak, locally sourced from Java.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Not applicable.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– I don't know

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:
– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
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– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

- ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - I don't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Notes: For e.g. each of the five Gapuros of the Ampel mosque represent a tenet of Islam: (a) Gapuro Puso (fasting); (b) Gapuro Madep (prayers); (c) Gapuro Mungguh (Haj pilgrimage); (d) Gapuro Ngamal (pious deeds); (e) Gapuro Panekan (credo).

- ↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
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- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - I don't know

- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - I don't know

- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes

- ↳ Humans
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Not applicable.

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Notes: The gist of Sunan Ampel's teachings are embodied in the Javanese notion of " Moh Limo," or refrain from five vices: (a) Moh main (no gambling); (b) Moh ngomboe (abstinence from liquor); (c) Moh maling (no stealing); (d) Moh madat (no opium); (e) Moh madon (proscription of extra-marital relations).

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Moh Limo as mentioned above.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: Adherence to the five tenets of Islam.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

–optional (common)

Notes: On the 23rd night of Ramadan, pilgrims congregate at Sunan Ampel to meditate and recite select verses from the Al-Quran.

–optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 10,000 per day

Notes: 50,000 per day during the month of Ramadan.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: During the holy month of Ramadan. Devotees congregate at Masjid Agung Sunan Ampel during the last ten days of the Holy Month to meditate.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Weekly recitation from the Al-Quran on Wednesday, known locally as "Dino Rebo Pengosan". The congregation is led by a Kyai (a Javanese Islamic expert).

– Yes

Reference: Kusumo, Eko Sulitsyo. "Bentuk Sinkretisme Islam-jawa Di Masjid Sunan Ampel Surabaya". *Mozaik Humaniora* 15, no. 1 (January 15, 2015).

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: Not applicable

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Through prayers offered by the devotees and the juru kunci (caretaker of the shrine).

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Visitors communicate with Allah through prayers. The Juru Kunci (caretaker) of the tomb also offers Tahlil (praises to the Almighty).

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– No

↳ Cleansing

– No

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The well within the precincts of Masjid Sunan Ampel is believed to have healing properties.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

–specify: Annual (Last ten days of the Holy Month of Ramadan).

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

–All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

–number: At least 1000-1500 on weekends.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: The Juru Kunci (caretaker of the tomb of Sunan Ampel) offers prayers at the shrine on behalf of the devotees.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The Juru Kunci is the caretaker of the tomb of Sunan Ampel.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– No

↳ Are they sky deity:
– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: Not applicable

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Through prayers offered by the devotees and the juru kunci (caretaker of the shrine).

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Notes: The gist of Sunan Ampel's teachings are embodied in the Javanese notion of "Moh Limo," or refrain from five vices: (a) Moh main (no gambling); (b) Moh ngomboc (abstinence from liquor); (c) Moh maling (no stealing); (d) Moh madat (no opium); (e) Moh madon (proscription of extra-marital relations).

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Moh Limo as mentioned above.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:
– Other [specify]: Adherence to the five tenets of Islam.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:
– Yes

Notes: Visitors communicate with Allah through prayers. The Juru Kunci (caretaker) of the tomb also offers Tahlil (praises to the Almighty).

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 10,000 per day

Notes: 50,000 per day during the month of Ramadan.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: During the holy month of Ramadan. Devotees congregate at Masjid Agung Sunan Ampel during the last ten days of the Holy Month to meditate.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Weekly recitation from the Al-Quran on Wednesday, known locally as "Dino Rebo Pengosan". The congregation is led by a Kyai (a Javanese Islamic expert).

– Yes

Reference: Kusumo, Eko Sulitsyo. "Bentuk Sinkretisme Islam-jawa Di Masjid Sunan Ampel Surabaya". *Mozaik Humaniora* 15, no. 1 (January 15, 2015).

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: The Juru Kunci (caretaker of the tomb of Sunan Ampel) offers prayers at the shrine on behalf of the devotees.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The Juru Kunci is the caretaker of the tomb of Sunan Ampel.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Notes: On the 23rd night of Ramadan, pilgrims congregate at Sunan Ampel to meditate and recite select verses from the Al-Quran.

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Annual (Last ten days of the Holy Month of Ramadan).

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: At least 1000-1500 on weekends.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– No

↳ Cleansing

– No

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The well within the precincts of Masjid Sunan Ampel is believed to have healing properties.

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Sunan Ampel Great Mosque, Surabaya, Sunyoto, Agus. *Buku Pertama Yang Mengungkap Wali Songo Sebagai Fakta Sejarah*. Bandung: Pustaka IIMaN, Trans Pustaka dan LTN PBNU, 2017.

Reference: Sunan Ampel Great Mosque, Surabaya, Spat, C.. *De Islam En Zijn Beteekende Voor Nederlandsch Indie*. Breda: De Koninklijke Militaire Akademi, 1925.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Kusumo, Eko Sulitsyo. "Bentuk Sinkretisme Islam-jawa Di Masjid Sunan Ampel Surabaya". *Mozaik Humaniora* 15, no. 1 (January 15, 2015).